

Efficacy of maize inbred testers with varying levels of resistance to *Striga* for classifying *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize lines into heterotic groups

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Abstract

Identifying efficient testers for separating maize (*Zea mays* L.) inbred lines into heterotic groups can facilitate the development of superior hybrids. *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred lines developed at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) do not have well established heterotic groups. This study was conducted to identify efficient testers for classifying yellow-maize inbred lines into heterotic groups. Thirty *Striga*-resistant inbred lines were crossed with three testers having varying levels of resistance to *Striga*. A trial comprising 90 testcrosses and two hybrid checks was conducted at two locations in Nigeria for two years under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions. The approach that involved specific combining ability (SCA) effects and mean grain yields was found to be more efficient than the heterotic group's specific and general combining ability (HSGCA) grouping method in separating the 30 inbred lines into three heterotic groups. The tolerant and resistant testers were highly efficient in grouping the inbred lines into heterotic groups under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions using the two approaches. *Striga*-resistant yellow inbred lines assigned to two of the three major heterotic groups could be used as parents for developing superior hybrids and/or synthetics and for generating source populations for developing new maize inbred lines.

Keywords: Heterotic grouping; *Striga hermonthica*; *Striga*-resistance; Testcrosses; Testers *Zea mays*

Introduction

Maize is a multipurpose crop cultivated for food, feed, and as a source of various industrial products. In sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America, it is mainly used for human consumption (Shiferaw et al. 2011). It is a good source of starch, protein, and fat, accounting for 72% starch, 10% protein, and 4% fat, supplying an energy density of 365 Kcal/100g compared with rice and wheat (Nuss and Tanumihardjo 2010). More than 25 million ha of land in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is planted to maize, primarily by smallholder farmers, producing 38 million metric

tons for food (Smale et al. 2013). The production of maize in SSA increased with an increase in the area under cultivation during the past years. However, the average yield of maize (<2 t/ha) in Africa is far less than the global average yield of 5.5 t/ha because of many abiotic and biotic factors, lack of access to quality improved seed and inputs, sub-optimal crop management practices (Smale et al. 2011; Buck 2017). The development and commercialization of stress-resilient maize hybrids can enhance the productivity gains under stressful growing conditions, contributing to grain outputs for satisfying the increasing demand for maize in SSA. The development of stress-resilient hybrids depends on the crossing of stress-tolerant maize inbred lines belonging to different well-established heterotic groups (Barata and Carena 2006). Stratification of white inbred lines into heterotic groups under the different environmental conditions has thus been undertaken by several researchers in SSA (Menkir and Badu-Apraku 2003; Menkir et al. 2004; Akinwale et al. 2014), but a continual assessment of the heterotic affinities of new maize inbred lines is still needed for ensuring improved management of elite breeding materials (Barata and Carena 2006).

Maize breeders at IITA have used diverse sources of resistance to develop yellow-maize inbred lines expressing varying levels of field resistance or tolerance to *S. hermonthica* (Kim 1991; Kling et al. 2000; Menkir et al. 2010). Understanding the heterotic affinities of *Striga-resistant* yellow-maize inbred lines with diverse genetic backgrounds that have not been characterized is important to select suitable parents for developing source populations for developing new inbred lines and generating superior hybrid combinations (Menkir et al. 2004). The line \times tester mating design has been widely used, as it is the simplest and fastest approach for evaluating the breeding values of inbred lines in hybrid combinations (Albrecht et al. 2014) and to separate lines into heterotic groups (Menkir et al. 2004; Sharma 2006; Rashid 2007; Ceyhan et al. 2008; Fato et al. 2012; Annor et al. 2020). Appropriate placement of new maize inbred lines into heterotic groups is determined by the type of tester used to generate crosses and evaluate them

across target locations, years, and stress conditions (Xia et al. 2005; Hallauer et al. 2010). When a large number of new inbred lines is generated in a breeding program, the relative performance of lines in testcrosses with known testers can be used as the main criterion for separating the lines into heterotic groups (Melchinger 1999).

The choice of appropriate testers has been considered critical to correctly classify inbred lines into heterotic groups in maize breeding programs (Guimarães et al. 2012). Several studies have indicated the usefulness of testers to classify inbred lines into heterotic groups but did not recommend specific testers that allow reliable evaluation for assignment of lines into groups (Dari et al. 2010; Hallauer et al. 2010; Fato et al. 2012; Guimarães et al. 2012; Mwimali et al. 2016). The most commonly used combining ability-based heterotic grouping has been based primarily on the mean yield of sets of inbred line with different testers (Gurung et al. 2009; Fan et al. 2009). However, Fato et al. (2012) reported that neither the resistant nor the susceptible tester had been successful in assigning all inbred lines into existing heterotic groups under downy mildew infestation, highlighting the need for additional testers to separate the remaining unclassified lines into heterotic groups. Furthermore, the capacity of testers with diverse resistance reactions to *S. hermonthica* that can accurately assign *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred lines into heterotic groups has not been determined yet. Hence, the aim of this study was to identify suitable testers that best classify the *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred lines into heterotic groups.

Materials and methods

Plant materials

Thirty yellow-endosperm *Striga*-resistant maize inbred lines and three testers with varying levels of resistance to *Striga* developed at IITA were used in this study. The genetic background

of the materials was described by Zebire et al. (2020). The lines were designated as L1-L30 and testers as T1 = tolerant, T2 = resistant and T3= susceptible. Among the 30 lines, 22 were derived from two biparental crosses of elite *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred lines, whereas the remaining eight *Striga*-resistant lines were derived from ACR97SYN-Y, a synthetic; TZE COMP5, an early composite; and ACR97TZL-COMP1, a late-maturing experimental variety. The three testers were TZISTR1207, a *Striga*-tolerant line (T1) derived from a backcross containing B73, a temperate inbred line; TZSTRI106, a *Striga*-resistant line (T2) derived from a backcross containing *Zea diploperennis* in its genome; and TZISTR1033, a *Striga*-susceptible line (T3) derived from a bi-parental cross between 9450, a temperate line and KI21, a line from Thailand. The 30 inbred lines were crossed to the three testers to generate 90 testcrosses, which were evaluated along with two checks having known tolerant and susceptible reactions to the parasite, under *Striga*-infested and *Striga*-non-infested conditions.

Experimental site description and fertilizer application

The experiment was conducted during the 2018 and 2019 main cropping season at Abuja (9^o15' N and 7^o20' E, with an altitude of 431 meters above sea level (masl) and Mokwa (9^o21' N and 5^o1' E, with an altitude of 188 masl), Nigeria, where *Striga* is endemic. Annual rainfall in Abuja was 1739 mm in 2018 and 2031 in 2019; respective values for Mokwa were 1152 and 993 mm. The soil at Abuja was sandy and had 0.5 g/kg nitrogen (N), 68.99 mg/kg phosphorous (P) and 0.25 cmol/kg potassium content, whereas the soil at Mokwa was sandy loam with 0.4 g/kg N, 31.5 mg/kg P and 0.10 cmol/kg K.

Experimental design and management

The 90 testcrosses and two checks were laid out in a 23 × 4 alpha lattice design, with two replications. Planting was carried out in a serpentine arrangement (Pearce 1976) in June at Abuja and in July at Mokwa. Each hybrid was planted in adjacent infested and non-infested

strips, separated by a 1.5 m alley. Within each strip, a testcross was planted in a single-row plot of 4 m length, with 0.75 m spacing between rows and 0.25 m spacing between plants within a row. The infested row of a testcross was planted directly opposite the respective non-infested row to obtain precise estimates of yield loss attributable to *S. hermonthica* damage (Kling et al. 2000). *Striga* infestation of the field was described by Zebire et al. (2020). Two maize seeds of a testcross were placed into the holes infested with sand-mixed *S. hermonthica* seeds and covered with soil. One plant was manually removed from each hill two weeks after planting to attain a population density of 53,333 plants per ha. Nitrogen fertilizer was applied at the rate of 30 kg per ha at planting, and an additional 30 kg/ha N was applied four weeks later. In addition, 60 kg/ha of each of P₂O₅ and K₂O were applied at planting. Weeds other than *S. hermonthica* were manually removed from infested and non-infested plots throughout the cropping season.

Data collection

Days to 50% anthesis and 50% silking were recorded as the number of days from planting to when 50% of the plants in a plot shed pollen and showed silk extrusion, respectively. Anthesis-silking interval was calculated as the difference between days to 50% silking and days to 50% anthesis. All ears were harvested from each plot. Field weight and grain weight (kg/ha); the weight of all cobs and grain after shelling per plot, respectively, were measured. Grain moisture (%) was taken from shelled grain with a moisture tester at harvest under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions. Grain yield (kg/ha) of the hybrids under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions for each plot was computed and adjusted to 15% grain moisture. Host plant damage symptoms were visually rated in each infested row at 8 and 10 weeks after planting (WAP) using a scale of 1 to 9, where 1 = no visible host plant damage symptom and 9 = all leaves completely scorched, resulting in premature death of the plant (Kim 1994). Also, the

total numbers of emerged *S. hermonthica* plants were counted in each infested row at 8 and 10 WAP on a plot basis.

Data analysis

The analysis was done according to Zebire et al. (2020). Each location-year combination was considered a test environment, and analyses of variance were computed for all traits measured under infested and non-infested conditions using PROC MIXED procedure in SAS 9.4 (SAS 2013). Combined analyses were conducted for traits measured under infested and non-infested conditions. In these analyses, environments and replication (environments) were considered random effects, whereas testcrosses were regarded as fixed effects. Further, line \times tester analysis was conducted by excluding the checks to partition the testcross mean square into lines, testers, line \times tester, whereas testcross \times environment mean square was also partitioned into line \times environment, tester \times environment, and line \times tester \times environment effects using a SAS program, following the procedure of Singh and Chaudhary (Singh and Chaudhary 1977). General combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) effects were also estimated to identify a pair of testers with significantly distinct GCA to assign the inbred lines to heterotic groups.

Heterotic grouping of the inbred lines was determined based on the SCA effect of testcross and mean grain yields, as suggested by Menkir et al. (2004), who classified inbred lines into heterotic groups following the combining ability effects and grain yield when crossed with flint and dent maize testers. In the present study, based on this procedure, inbred lines were assigned to heterotic group A (HGA), when its cross with a tolerant tester (T1) showed a large positive SCA value and mean grain yield performance was greater than or equal to mean grain yield performance across testers, otherwise, it was assigned to heterotic groups B (HGB) or C (HGC)

when the crosses showed positive SCA and greater mean grain yield performance than the reciprocal cross with the resistant (T2) or susceptible (T3) testers.

An alternative approach, known as heterotic group's specific and general combining ability (HSGCA), based on the combined use of GCA and SCA to assign inbred lines to heterotic groups has been proposed to overcome the limitations of the SCA-based grouping method (Fan et al. 2009). This method was applied by modifying the direction of assigning heterotic grouping; Fan et al. (2009) used a negative SCA estimate. However, the inbred lines were assigned to heterotic groups following a positive effect of SCA because the testers used to exhibit a different reaction to *Striga* resistance. The method is briefly described below;

1. Compute SCA and GCA effect following the procedure outlined by Singh and Chaudhary (1977)
2. Calculate HSGCA effect based on the formula described by Fan et al. (2009), which is as shown below:

$$\text{HSGCA} = \text{Cross mean } X_{ij} - \text{Tester mean } (X_i) = \text{GCA} + \text{SCA}$$

where X_{ij} = interaction mean of line and tester and X_i = tester mean

3. Based on HSGCA value, inbred lines with positive HSGCA effects were assigned to the same heterotic groups as their tester.
4. When an inbred line was assigned to more than one heterotic group in Step 3, we kept the line in the heterotic group depending on the HSGCA effect, i.e., if its HSGCA had the largest value and otherwise removed it from other heterotic groups.
5. If a line had a negative HSGCA effect with all representative testers with varying levels of *Striga* resistance reaction, the inbred lines were assigned to any heterotic carefully.

Genetic distance-based clustering using DarTseq SNP markers

Young growing leaves at the 3-leaf to 4-leaf stage were collected from maize plants grown in the field for DNA extraction. Leaves were collected from 4 to 15 leaves of each line and tester and then bulked. The samples were stored in a deep freezer at -80°C . Each sample was dried in a Labconco Freezone 2.5L system lyophilizer (Marshall Scientific, USA) before extracting genomic DNA. The extraction of the gDNA was carried out according to the DArT protocol ([www.diversityarrays.com/files/ DaRT_DNA_isolation.pdf](http://www.diversityarrays.com/files/DaRT_DNA_isolation.pdf)). The quality and quantity of the DNA were checked via gel electrophoresis using 0.8% agarose gel and NANODROP[®] spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Denver, CO, USA). The samples were sent to the Diversity Array technology company (Jaccoud et al. 2001). All protocols, including Library construction, sequencing, and SNP calling, were performed at the Diversity Arrays facility in Canberra, Australia.

A total of 27,874 SNP markers generated from the present maize panel was received from the DArTseq platform. The SNPs were further filtered using TASSEL software (Bradbury et al. 2007) to maintain only polymorphic SNPs with a maximum of 10% missing values and a minimum and maximum allele frequency of 0.05 and 0.95, respectively. The final filtered data comprised 6081 SNP markers for further analysis. Genetic distance was estimated between pairs of inbred lines for the 6081 marker data set using the identity-by-state (IBS) method and the genetic relationships among the 30 inbred lines and 3 testers were explored using Roger's genetic distance (GD) using PowerMaker version 3.25 (Liu and Muse, 2005). Cluster analysis was performed for the inbred lines and testers based on the genetic distance matrix with unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) with clustering algorithm via PowerMarker version 3.25 (Liu and Muse 2005) and viewed using MEGA, version 6.0 (Tamura et al. 2013).

Results

Analysis of variance for grain yield and other selected traits

In this paper, we mainly focused on the effect of testers with varying level of resistance to *Striga hermonthica* to classify *Striga*-resistant inbred lines into heterotic group. Environments (Env), testcrosses and testcross \times environment interactions mean squares were significant ($P < 0.05$) for grain yield and most of the measured agronomic traits across environments (Table 1). Line (GCA) and tester (GCA) mean squares were significant for all traits measured under both infested and non-infested conditions. The line \times tester (SCA) effect was significant only for grain yield under infestation and for *Striga* damage rating at 10 WAP across environments but not under non-infested conditions. The line (GCA) \times environment and tester (GCA) \times environment interaction mean squares were also significant for most of the traits (Table 1). In contrast, the SCA \times environment interaction mean squares were not significant for all the traits measured under the two growing conditions, except for *Striga* damage rating at 10 WAP under infestation.

Discriminative and representative ability of testers

The average environment coordinate (AEC), which in this case was a tester, was used to describe the efficiency of the testers. The discriminative ability of each tester is determined by the length of the vectors, which is nearly equal to the standard deviation (Yan and Kang 2002). In the present study, the tolerant (T1) and resistant (T2) testers had a longer vector than T3, the susceptible tester under both *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions (Figures 1 and 2). Consequently, T1 and T2 are considered more discriminating than T3. The representativeness of an individual tester is determined by its proximate angle with AEC; the smaller the angle between the tester vector and the AEC, the more representative the tester (Yan and Kang 2002). Thus, T3 was the most representative. In addition to the length of tester vectors, the relationship

among the testers was used to determine efficiency. Annor et al. (2020) reported that the cosine of the angle between any two tester vectors in a biplot indicates the correlation between the testers, with testers having a smaller angle between them being more closely related in classifying inbred lines into heterotic groups. These authors also suggested that testers with shorter vectors provide little or no information about the testcrosses evaluated compared to testers with longer vectors. In effect, the discriminative ability of the testers in this study can be ranked as $T2 > T1 > T3$.

Combining ability estimates

General combining ability (GCA) effects for grain yield under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions, *Striga* damage rating, *Striga* emergence count are presented in Table 2. Lines L1, L3, L12, and L14 combined significant positive GCA effects for grain yield in at least one of the growing conditions with negative GCA effects for *Striga* damage rating and emerged *Striga* count. Also, inbred line L6 had positive but non-significant GCA effects for grain yield under infested and non-infested conditions, significant and negative GCA effects for *Striga* damage rating and negative but not significant GCA effect for emerged *Striga* count. Lines L18, L23 and L25 all had positive and significant GCA effects in at least one of the growing conditions but generally had positive GCA effects for *Striga*-damage rating and emerged *Striga* count (Table 2). It is interesting to note that nine lines with negative GCA effects under *Striga* infestation had a positive GCA effect for *Striga* damage rating and emerged *Striga* count. Among the three testers, the tolerant (T1) and resistant testers (T2) combined significant positive GCA effects for grain yield under *Striga* infestation, with negative GCA effects for *Striga* damage rating and emerged *Striga* count (Table 2). These testers also had positive GCA effects for grain yield under the non-infested condition, with the GCA effect of the resistant tester being positive. In sharp contrast, the susceptible tester (T3) displayed significant ($P \leq$

0.01) negative GCA effects for grain yield under both the growing conditions, and positive and significant GCA effects for *Striga* damage ratings and emerged *Striga* count.

The SCA effects for grain yield varied considerably for each of the line \times tester combinations (Table 3). The number of testcrosses with positive SCA effect for grain yield under infestation was 14 for T1 (121-793 kg/ha), 14 for T2 (111-830 kg/ha) and nine for T3 (121-534 kg/ha). Also, testcrosses with positive SCA effects for grain yield under non-infested conditions were 11 for T1 (109-951 kg/ha), 15 for T2 (100-761 kg/ha) and 12 for T3 (105-429 kg/ha). Most of the testcrosses involving each tester with positive SCA effects under infestation also had positive SCA effects under non-infested conditions. For grain yield, the average SCA estimates ranged from -968.1 to 1085.6 kg/ha (Table 3). Six hybrids had the highest positive SCA effect under *Striga* infestation, which was obtained in L29 \times T1, L30 \times T1, L6 \times T2, L15 \times T2, L20 \times T2 and L25 \times T2, whereas four crosses, viz., L9 \times T1, L28 \times T1, L29 \times T1 and L6 \times T2, had the highest values under non-infested condition (Table 3). Tester T2 under *Striga*-infested and T1 under *Striga* non-infested conditions were appropriate testers for evaluating the combining ability of the lines for superior grain yield production.

SCA effect and grain yield-based heterotic grouping

The three testers successfully discriminated among the 30 inbred lines with unknown heterotic patterns under *Striga* infestation. Based on SCA and grain yield (Table 3), under *Striga*-infestation, lines were classified into three heterotic groups, designated as HGA, HGB and HGC. HGA consisted of 13 inbred lines that showed positive SCA effects in crosses with the tolerant tester (T1), whereas HGB comprised 13 inbred lines that displayed positive SCA effects in crosses with the resistant tester (T2). Two lines having positive SCA effects in crosses with both T1 and T2 were assigned to both HGA and HGB, whereas the remaining two inbred lines

with positive SCA effects in crosses only with T3 were assigned to HGC (Table 3). Under the non-infested condition, 11 inbred lines with positive SCA effects in crosses with T1 were assigned to HGA, and 13 lines with positive SCA effects in crosses with T2 were assigned to HGB, and three inbred lines that showed positive SCA effects in crosses with both T1 and T2 were assigned to both HGA and HGB. There were three lines with positive SCA effects in crosses with only T3 that were assigned to HGC under non-infested condition. It is interesting to note that eight inbred lines assigned to HGA using the tolerant (T1) tester and nine inbred lines assigned to HGB using the resistant (T2) testers were common across both infested and non-infested conditions. Therefore, the tolerant and resistant inbred testers can be effectively used to assesses the combining ability of the new inbred lines and assigning them to different heterotic groups.

Heterotic group's specific and general combining ability (HSGCA)-based heterotic grouping

The HSGCA method of grouping also classified the 30 *Striga*-resistant yellow-endosperm inbred lines into three heterotic groups, similar to the grouping based on GCA and SCA (Table 4). This method assigned 10, 10, and 7 inbred lines to HGA, HGB and HGC, respectively, under *Striga* infestation but failed to group three inbred lines into any of the three heterotic groups (Table 4). Similarly, 11 lines were assigned to HGA, 10 lines were assigned to HGB, and 5 lines were assigned to HGC using the HSGCA method under *Striga* non-infested condition (Table 4). Again, this method did not assign four inbred lines to any of the three heterotic groups under non-infested condition. Eight inbred lines assigned to HGA using the tolerant (T1) tester, five inbred lines assigned to HGB using the resistant (T2) testers and two inbred lines assigned to HGC using the susceptible (T3) tester were common across both infested and non-infested conditions. It was interesting to note the SCA-based and HSGCA methods commonly assigned 10 lines to HGA, nine lines to HGB and one line to HGC under *Striga* infestation. Also, these

methods had similarly assigned 11 lines to HGA, 10 lines to HGB and three lines to HGC under the non-infested condition.

Grouping derived from cluster analysis using molecular marker

The GD estimates between pairs of 30 lines and three testers were calculated based on 6081 SNP markers. A broad range of GD values was estimated from inbred lines derived from ACR97SYN-Y-S1-79-B*4 and TZE COMP5, with the highest GD value of 0.45 (Table 4.5). Lines from the same genetic background had low GD values. A dendrogram based on molecular marker-based GD of 30 yellow *Striga*-resistant inbred lines and three testers showed two main groups (Figure 3). The first subgroup (C-I) consisted of 23 inbred lines, most of which are derived from ACR97SYN-Y-S1-79-B*4, ACR97SYN-Y-S1-24-B*4 and ACR97TZLComp1-YS155 and all the three testers. The second Group (Group-II) comprised seven inbred lines derived mainly from TZE COMP5.

DISCUSSION

Assigning new maize inbred lines to different heterotic groups can play a significant role in hybrid breeding programs (Hallauer et al. 2010). Maize breeders classify maize inbred lines into heterotic groups using testcross performance and SCA with testers of known genetic backgrounds and heterotic relations (Vasal et al. 1992; Menkir et al. 2004; Adebayo et al. 2014). The observed significant variations among lines and testers indicate that the testers can classify the diverse maize inbred lines into heterotic groups. The significant effects of GCA and SCA also indicate that both the additive and non-additive effects are important for grain yield and other traits measured in the present study. The significant environment \times tester interaction for grain yield could be attributable to the differential effect of testers across environments, consistent with the result of EL-Honary (2014), who reported that testers were more affected by environmental conditions than lines.

Among the inbred lines evaluated in the present study, L12 combined the highest and positive GCA effect for grain yield under infestation, with significant and negative GCA effects for *Striga* damage rating and *Striga* emergence count at 8 and 10 WAP. Also, lines L1, L3, and L14 were found to be good general combiners for grain yield under both infested and non-infested conditions and *Striga* damage symptoms and emerged *Striga* count, the four inbred lines (L1, L3, L6, and L12) can thus be used as desirable parents for the development of new hybrids targeted for areas infested with *S. hermonthica*. Many inbred lines included in this study had negative GCA effects for grain yield under infested and non-infested conditions, similar to the results reported in the breeding material used for grain yield and other morphological traits in other studies (Menkir et al. 2004; Legesse et al. 2009). Among the yellow testers, the resistant tester derived from Z.diplo.BC4 population had the largest GCA effects for grain yield, followed by the tolerant tester under both growing conditions. These testers also had negative GCA effects for *Striga* damage rating and emerged *Striga* count, demonstrating that they should be valuable testers to enhance productivity and resistance to *S. hermonthica*.

The relative performance of inbred lines in testcrosses with known testers helps to determine heterotic grouping of lines (Melchinger 1999). Among the 30 inbred lines crossed with three testers, nearly 50% of the lines crossed to each tester showed positive SCA effects for grain yield, particularly under *Striga* infestation. The inbred lines with similar genetic backgrounds did not show similar affinity to any of the tester parents based on yield-based SCA effects, suggesting that the testers were heterotic to each other. All the *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred lines but two with positive SCA effects in crosses with the tolerant tester had negative SCA effects in crosses with the resistant tester. Estimates of SCA effects are routinely used for the selection and breeding of superior hybrids (Badu-Apraku and Akinwale 2019). As also observed in other studies, parents that are genetically diverse and form desirable crosses,

resulting in superior agronomic performance, exhibit high SCA effects (Fan et al. 2001; Legesse et al. 2009).

The availability of efficient testers that effectively discriminate and classify inbred lines into appropriate heterotic groups determines the success in developing high-yielding hybrids and synthetic varieties (Annor et al. 2020). Inbred lines were assigned to HGA when they showed large positive SCA effects and mean performance was greater than or equal to mean performance across testers, otherwise they were assigned to HGB or HGC (Menkir et al. 2004). The two testers were able to classify 28 of the 30 tested lines under *Striga* infestation and 27 of the 30 tested inbred lines under non-infested conditions into HGA and HGB heterotic groups. Vasal et al. (1992) also reported that two out of four testers grouped tropical and subtropical inbred lines into heterotic groups based on the contrasting SCA effects. Inbred lines exhibiting both positive SCA effects with both the tolerant and resistant testers were classified into both HGA and HGB groups. These results are in agreement with the finding of Menkir et al. (2004), who reported 15 of 38 inbred lines showing outstanding testcross performance when crossed to the two testers and assigned to either of the heterotic groups, with some lines combining equally well with the two testers representing different heterotic groups. When such a situation occurs, (Geadelmann 1984) suggests that the breeder must choose one of the two groups.

The HSGCA grouping method separated the lines into three heterotic groups and left a few lines not assigned to the three heterotic groups under both infested and non-infested conditions. The tolerant (T1) and resistant (T2) testers classified most of the inbred lines into the respective heterotic groups, suggesting that these testers were suitable for classifying inbred lines into heterotic groups. Though all the 30 *Striga*-resistant maize inbred lines were assigned to the three heterotic groups based on SCA effects and mean grain yields under both infested and non-infested conditions, HSGCA-based grouping was unable to assign some lines to any of the three

groups under the same growing conditions. The HSGCA method of heterotic grouping was reported to be the most predictable as it involved both the GCA effects of the lines and the SCA effects of line \times tester combinations (Fan et al. 2009). In the present study, 67% of the lines under *Striga* infestation, which were assigned to the three groups via the SCA-based grouping, were also assigned to the same three heterotic groups based on the HSGCA grouping method. Similarly, 80% of the lines under the non-infested condition that were assigned to the same heterotic group based on SCA-based grouping were also assigned to the same three heterotic groups based on the HSGCA grouping method. The fact that some resistant inbred lines were not assigned to any of the three heterotic groups based on the HSGCA grouping method, this method offered no additional advantage in this study.

Many studies examined the use of molecular marker-based genetic similarities and combining ability analysis and complementary tools for accurate assignment of parental lines to heterotic groups (Menkir et al. 2004; Barata and Carena 2006; Fan et al. 2009). In a separate study, the 30 *Striga*-resistant yellow inbred lines were subjected to genetic distance-based clustering based on the DArTseq SNP markers (unpublished data). The composition of the resulting two major genetic distance-based clusters was different from the composition of the lines assigned to the three heterotic groups established based on SCA effects for grain yield. This agrees with the result of Barata and Carena 2006), who reported the existence of large inconsistencies between the molecular marker and field data. Ertiro et al. (2017) reported that SNP markers separated CIMMYT maize lines into heterotic groups A and B based on pedigree information and combining ability though the grouping was not distinct enough. Pinto et al. (2003) reported the assignment of S₃ lines to heterotic groups using restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers and estimates of SCA. Molecular markers can be successfully used to study the genetic diversity of inbred lines, but it may not necessarily increase the efficiency of heterosis prediction based on clusters produced (Barata and Carena 2006). It is also known that

combining ability-based heterotic grouping can be affected by the type of tester used, the genetic background of the inbred line and the number of environments used for the trials (Ertiro et al. 2017). Thus, the prediction of hybrid performance and classifying inbred lines into heterotic groups with molecular markers should be complemented and validated with field testing.

CONCLUSION

Determining heterotic groups of *Striga*-resistant yellow-maize inbred line can facilitate the selection of parents to be used for the development of superior hybrids with high level of resistance to *S. hermonthica*. In the present study, the testers were able to classify 27 to 28 tested inbred lines into two of the three heterotic groups based on SCA effects and testcross mean grain yields under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions. The HSGCA method also classified the inbred lines into three heterotic groups following based the different testers used in the study. The tolerant and resistant testers showed better efficiency in classifying inbred lines into heterotic groups under both growing conditions using the two approaches. These testers could thus be utilized not only for classifying *Striga*-resistant yellow inbred lines into heterotic groups but also for identifying parental lines with good combining ability to develop superior hybrids for *Striga*-infested areas. The inbred lines separated into heterotic groups will be used to develop hybrids as well as for recycling maize inbred lines.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

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1 **Tables**

2 **Table 1.** Mean squares from analysis of variance of testcrosses for some selected traits evaluated across environments under *Striga*-infested and non-infested
3 conditions

Source of variation	DF	Grain yield	Grain yield	<i>Striga</i> damage		Emerged <i>Striga</i> count		Silking	Anthesis
		(infested)	(non-infested)	rating(1-9)		(no.)		-----Days-----	
		-----Kg/ha-----		8 WAP†	10 WAP	8 WAP	10 WAP		
Env	3	468026713***	323822482.5***	76.8***	208.0***	133089.7***	486970.1***	5509.5***	5663.3***
Testcross	89	3214385***	2865918.4***	2.92***	4.86***	1249.47***	1933.8***	25.4***	22.3***
Line (GCA)	29	2583503***	2641094.2*	2.97***	4.49***	2152.19***	2770.88***	39.9***	34.7***
Tester (GCA)	2	55710267***	39634973.7***	57.4***	95.4***	5957.6***	4949.4*	426.0***	389.1***
Line × Tester (SCA)	58	1719623**	1710433	1.02	1.93**	635.76	1411.21	4.1	3.5
Testcross × Env	267	1131521	1510982.2	1.2***	2.2***	609.1	1420.2**	4.18**	3.87***
Line × Env	87	1181929	1142066	1.53***	2.40***	716.15*	1298.8	5.7***	5.4***
Tester × Env	6	3695027**	7541546.2***	8.2***	14.0***	1304.0*	2683.1*	11.9**	15.7***
Line × Tester × Env	174	1017921	1487490	0.7	1.7**	531.7	1437.3	3.2	2.7
Error	359	1108721	1565284	0.8	1.2	535	1240.5	3.4	2.8
CV (%)		23.2	27.8	24.3	20.8	60	52.1	2.4	2.3

4 *, **, *** Significant at < 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 probability level, respectively.

5 †WAP= Weeks after planting.

6

7 **Table 2.** General combining ability effects for grain yield under *Striga*-infested and non-infested
8 conditions, *Striga* damage rating at 8 and 10 weeks after planting (WAP) and *Striga* emergence count
9 at 8 WAP and 10 WAP.

Lines†	Grain yield	Grain yield	<i>Striga</i> damage rating(1-9)		Emerging <i>Striga</i> count	
	(infested)	(non-infested)	8 WAP	10 WAP	8 WAP	10 WAP
	(Kg/ha)	(Kg/ha)			(no.)	(no.)
L1	456.14*	180.68	-0.39	-0.61*	-8.03	-10.45
L2	-132.84	255.87	0.36	-0.15	-1.49	-4.53
L3	609.74**	534.57**	-0.47	-0.36	-13.91**	-13.95
L4	-121.29	-381.94	0.49*	0.56	2.05	-1.66
L5	-206.77	279.46	0.20	0.52	-2.66	-4.07
L6	314.88	221.56	-0.72**	-0.69*	-0.70	-0.66
L7	-123.49	-185.98	-0.05	0.31	3.34	5.59
L8	-264.85	22.88	0.28	0.31	24.39***	21.84**
L9	-362.11	-540.51**	-0.59*	-0.52	1.76	5.05
L10	12.59	-23.26	-0.39	-0.44	-6.95	-9.95
L11	-125.71	-356.62	-0.01	-0.11	3.84	-0.41
L12	721.07***	139.18	-0.30	-0.82**	-17.19**	-19.99**
L13	-602.34**	-301.15	0.16	0.35	3.39	4.72
L14	561.29**	262.80	-0.30	-0.48	-8.36	-4.24
L15	-331.54	-269.46	0.11	0.35	-0.16	-2.03
L16	-76.57	-90.85	-0.22	-0.02	-3.11	5.88
L17	53.95	-115.23	0.49*	0.18	-9.28	-10.53
L18	317.22	531.85**	0.20	0.18	-4.16	-2.12
L19	96.51	-176.52	-0.22	0.43	-1.16	7.05
L20	-160.33	-50.12	0.24	0.10	0.14	-0.03
L21	-62.86	-607.91**	-0.05	-0.15	0.97	-1.03
L22	-174.22	-160.42	0.16	0.52	11.72*	12.72
L23	441.14*	285.67	-0.01	0.02	15.68**	15.22*
L24	-210.53	-132.18	0.11	-0.11	-7.82	-9.24
L25	337.84	617.58**	0.61*	0.27	17.93***	13.18
L26	-149.67	133.47	-0.26	-0.65*	-0.41	-6.03
L27	-216.34	501.90*	0.28	0.43	14.14**	19.59**
L28	-31.09	177.56	-0.39	-0.23	3.47	16.47*
L29	-105.88	-497.22*	0.11	-0.07	-12.86*	-17.32*
L30	-462.92*	-255.66	0.57*	0.85**	-4.57	-9.07
GCASE	218.19	214.48	0.25	0.31	5.37	7.23
Testers						
T1‡	221.40*	149.20	-0.39*	-0.59**	-0.46	-1.14
T2§	331.29**	310.69*	-0.15	-0.07	-4.74*	-3.87
T3¶	-552.69***	-459.79**	0.55**	0.66**	5.19*	5.00
GCASE	101.30	144.74	0.15	0.20	1.90	2.73

10 *, **, *** Significant at < 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 probability level, respectively.

11 †L1- L30 = the 30 inbred lines.

12 ‡T1= tolerant tester.

13 §T2 = resistant tester.

14 ¶T3 = susceptible tester.

Table 3. Mean grain yield, specific combining ability (SCA) effects and yield-and SCA-based heterotic grouping (HG) of 30 *Striga*-resistant yellow maize inbred lines under *Striga*-infested and non-infested conditions

Lines [†]	<i>Striga</i> infested							<i>Striga</i> non-infested						
	Grain yield (kg/ha)			SCA effect (kg/ha)			HG	Grain yield (kg/ha)			SCA effect (kg/ha)			HG
	T1 [‡]	T2 [§]	T3 [¶]	T1	T2	T3		T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	
L1	4016	4315	3488	-145	44	101	B	4536	5161	4323	-287	177	110	B
L2	3228	3625	3199	-344	-57	401	C	4454	5298	4494	-444	239	205	B
L3	4610	3595	4074	296	-830	534	A	5034	5310	4738	-143	-28	171	C
L4	3281	3974	2833	-303	280	23	B	3891	4634	3807	-369	213	156	B
L5	3356	3719	2756	-142	111	32	B	4799	5365	4153	-123	282	-160	B
L6	3714	4960	2721	-305	830	-525	B	4387	5786	3970	-476	761	-285	B
L7	3706	3861	2512	125	170	-295	AB	4410	4434	4076	-46	-183	229	C
L8	3879	3745	2032	439	195	-634	AB	4866	4744	3936	202	-82	-119	A
L9	3821	2834	2709	479	-619	141	A	4820	4008	3029	718	-255	-463	A
L10	4066	3545	2877	349	-282	-67	A	5021	4589	3799	402	-192	-211	A
L11	3515	3947	2611	-64	258	-195	B	4318	4016	4075	32	-431	399	A
L12	4204	4895	3515	-222	359	-137	B	4523	5381	3992	-258	438	-180	B
L13	2913	3136	2595	-190	-77	267	C	3965	4773	3837	-376	271	105	B
L14	4286	4272	3576	20	-104	84	A	5213	5027	4027	308	-40	-269	A
L15	3064	4041	2351	-309	557	-249	B	4465	4617	3587	93	83	-176	AB
L16	3124	3841	3256	-504	103	402	B	4239	5174	3793	-313	461	-149	B
L17	3923	3696	2990	165	-172	6	A	4314	4641	4177	-212	-47	259	C
L18	4068	3946	3388	46	-186	140	A	5091	5717	4266	-83	382	-299	B
L19	3922	3745	3074	121	-167	46	A	4649	4785	3514	184	158	-342	AB
L20	2823	4255	2891	-722	601	121	B	4829	4470	4029	237	-283	46	A
L21	3795	3688	2779	153	-64	-89	A	4073	4296	3286	39	100	-139	AB
L22	3027	3754	3147	-504	113	391	B	3745	4989	4264	-737	346	391	B
L23	3762	4675	3337	-384	419	-35	B	4663	5298	4374	-265	209	56	B
L24	3085	4115	2619	-410	511	-101	B	3793	5219	4070	-717	547	169	B
L25	3478	4728	3258	-564	575	-11	B	5288	5652	4391	29	231	-259	B
L26	3918	3320	2763	363	-345	-18	A	4885	4814	4180	109	-123	14	A
L27	3681	3466	2655	192	-132	-60	A	5340	5162	4482	197	-144	-53	A
L28	4162	3277	2918	488	-506	18	A	5514	4103	4394	695	-878	184	A
L29	4685	2741	2707	1086	-968	-118	A	5096	2926	3965	951	-1380	429	A
L30	4035	2734	2293	793	-618	-175	A	5038	3715	3957	652	-833	180	A
SE [±]	89	105	79	286	286	286		87	116	66	346	346	346	

[†]L1- L30 = the 30 inbred lines.

[‡]T1= tolerant tester.

[§]T2 = resistant tester.

[¶]T3 = susceptible tester.

[±]SE = standard error

Table 4. Heterotic grouping of 30 *Striga*-resistant yellow maize inbred lines based on Heterotic Grouping with Specific and General Combining Ability (HSGCA) of grain yield under infested and non-infested conditions

HGA (T1) ‡	HGB (T2) §	HGC (T3) ¶	Ungrouped
<i>Striga</i> infested			
L8, L9, L10, L17, L19, L21, L26, L28, L29 and L30	L4, L6, L7, L11, L12, L15, L20, L23, L24 and L25	L1, L2, L3, L14, L16, L18 and L22	L5, L13 and L27
<i>Striga</i> non-infested			
L8, L9, L10, L14, L19, L20, L26, L27, L28, L29 and L30	L1, L2, L5, L6, L12, L16, L18, L23, L24 and L25	L3, L7, L11, L17 and L22	L4, L13, L15 and L21

†L1- L30 = the 30 inbred lines.

‡T1= tolerant tester.

§T2 = resistant tester.

¶T3 = susceptible tester.

Figures

Figure 1. Average environment coordinate (AEC) vector view of genotype main effect plus genotype by tester biplot showing the discriminating power and representativeness of the testers across environments for grain yield under *Striga* infestation. T1 = tolerant tester, T2 = resistant tester and T3 = susceptible tester, and L1-L30 = the 30 inbred lines.

Figure 2. Average environment coordinate (AEC) vector view of genotype main effect plus genotype by tester biplot showing the discriminating power and representativeness of the testers across environments for grain yield under *Striga* non-infested condition. T1 = tolerant tester, T2 = resistant tester and T3 = susceptible tester, and L1-L30 = the 30 inbred lines.

Figure 3. Dendrogram of 30 *Striga*-resistant maize inbred lines based on roger's genetic distance values using 6081 single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) markers. T1 = tolerant tester, T2 = resistant tester and T3 = susceptible tester, and L1-L30 = the 30 inbred lines.